

CLASSIFICATION OF ECONOMIC RESOURCES IN INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES AND THEIR EFFECT ON SOCIO-ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

Doniyorova Shakhnoza Doniyorovna

Tashkent State University of Economics, independent researcher

Email: doniyorovashaxnoza78@gmail.com

Mobile: 94 207-12-26

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Abstract: In the article classification of economic resources in industrial enterprises and their impact on socio-economic development analyzed in the context of the development of modern industries. Also, the system of economic resources in an industrial enterprise requires a certain set of resources necessary for the organization of production processes. scientifically based.

Keywords: industrial sector, production, enterprise, resources, industrial economy, efficiency, factor, cost, criterion, finance, economic resources, social need, labor efficiency.

Introduction

The economic reforms implemented in Uzbekistan are aimed at solving the goals and tasks of proportional socio-economic development of regions. The stratification of socio-economic development of regions is primarily related to the diversity and difference of economic resources of regions, which creates the risk of a decrease in the level of socio-economic development not only for individual regions, but also for the entire country in the context of increased global competition. Therefore, this problem can be solved only by effective use of existing economic resources in the regions.

Effective use of regional economic resources is included in national and regional development programs. In general, "development" generally refers to any progressive change. Such an approach ensures that all progressive actions of the state's socio-economic policy are aimed at achieving a certain level by the regions. From year to year, a certain level of stratification occurs not only between regions, but also between sub-systems within the region, and problems in the form of socio-economic stratification increase. Even in the socio-economic development of regions at the district level, significant differences appear. Therefore, in the current economic transformation processes, it is necessary to increase their resource potential for sustainable development of regions. This is determined by the priorities of the potential in a particular area.

Analysis of literature on the subject

Research scientists have given many definitions to economic resources as an economic term, taking into account various aspects of enterprise activity, and scientific approaches are based on them. In particular: K. McConnell and S. Brew [1, vol. 1. - 1992. - 339 p.; t. 2 - 1992. - 400 p.] said that the concept of "economic resources" means all natural, human and man-made resources used for the production of goods and services. In the source of the dictionary "Bolshoy ekonomicheskii slovar" published under the editorship of AN Azriliyan [2, 776 p.], economic resources are defined as: "Factors of production are elements necessary for the production of products, goods and services."

According to Russian scientists R. Nureev, ADS Mirnov [3, 440 p.]: "Economic resources (or factors of production) are elements used for the production of economic products: in modern society, the most important of them are land, labor, capital (including its organization entrepreneurship skills and information" was researched. MKBunkina, VASemenov [4, 272 p.] say: "A large mass of goods intended for sale are utility services in material form. Four main factors interact in their production: natural resources, labor, capital and entrepreneurship.

Also, BA Reisberg [5, 716 p.] believes that factors are parameters that determine the nature and efficiency of economic processes.

Research methodology

In the research process, the scientific basis of the methodological approach to the development of economic resources in industrial enterprises, the formation of economic resources, the main directions of the use of economic resources, the indicators of the evaluation of the effectiveness of the use of these resources in industrial enterprises, the integrated economic effect obtained from the use of economic resources in industrial enterprises, the direction of increasing economic efficiency. A systematic and scientific approach, comparative and comparative analysis and grouping methods were used to study economic systems and ratios.

Analysis and results

The economic activity of an industrial enterprise is effective only if it has the necessary production resources. The results of the activities of the enterprises directly depend on the resources at their disposal, a sufficient amount of which is necessary for production activities, income generation and strengthening of competitive positions in the market. Each industrial enterprise has a unique set of resources, therefore, the enterprise must develop its own resource system that determines the results of activity. Without a reasonable

system of resources, the advantages and available opportunities of the enterprise compared to similar organizations and enterprises will be at a low level.

Figure 1. Diagram of the interrelationship of economic resources in industrial enterprises*

Source: developed by the author.

The system of resources in an industrial enterprise requires a certain set of resources necessary for the organization of production processes, the existing resources must meet the requirements of complementarity, mobility and exchange and correspond to the modern level of production (1- picture).

The composition of economic resources in production structures consists of the following:

- natural resources (land, underground resources, water, forest and biological, climate and recreation resources);
- labor resources (people capable of working);
- capital (money, means of production);
- entrepreneurial skills (people's ability to organize the production of goods and services);
- knowledge and skills necessary for economic activity.

Each economic resource forms its own resource market: labor market, capital market, etc., which in turn consist of many markets for a given resource.

Taking into account that economic resources are a set of material and immaterial factors and tools that ensure the social production activity, the continuous process of social production and reproduction, it is necessary to be especially careful in their classification. The functioning of the regional economy includes the use of economic resources. Resources involved in the process of reproduction act as factors of production and reproduction. Economic resources can be divided into real and potential resources.

As a basis for classification, the classification of economic benefits consists of the following [6]:

1. Long-term - renewable resources.
2. Short-term - fully consumed resources.
3. Exchangeable - alternative resources.
4. Complementary – complementary resources.
5. Real - resources at the direct disposal of the economic entity.
6. Future - potential potential resources.
7. Direct - direct satisfaction of some need.
8. Indirect or production - resources that satisfy any need as a means.

All economic resources are useful, limited (reserves are limited), resource capacity.

The usefulness of resources is that with their support the needs of the economy are met. The rarity of resources means that they are available in limited quantities. Limited resources can be compared with the unlimited needs of natural causes (in rare cases), social conditions and economic activity.

Resource intensity indicates the fact of using factors of production and the process of their creation. According to the share of costs, economic resources can be divided into types with high labor capacity, capital capacity and material capacity.

Economic resources created by nature are called free because they do not require human labor and tools used in the production process.

According to the form of the item, economic resources are divided into tangible and intangible types. Intangible resources are represented by categories that describe the quality and level in the process of mastering any quality.

From the point of view of socio-economic development of society, economic resources can be divided into:

- necessary resources for production;
- communication resources;
- information resources;
- business resources;
- community resources;
- social (educational, health care, etc.) resources.

According to their purpose, economic resources are divided into consumption (final consumption) and production (reproduced and repeatedly consumed) types.

It is known that some economists-scientists do not distinguish the exact classification of economic resources, except for those with a general description (natural, labor, production, entrepreneurial abilities, capital). This situation complicates the study of laws and reactions of socio-economic systems to the influence of economic resources.

Therefore, it is possible to use a systematic approach to carry out a scientific classification of economic resources and to determine the elements of the economic resources of the region in the general territorial socio-economic system [7]. The study of the essence of the regional socio-economic system justifies the need to clarify the fundamental concept of "system" from the point of view of the economic resources of the region. Therefore, NNMoiseev calls any set of interacting elements a "system". Obviously, this interpretation allows us to formally clarify the concept by listing its properties [8]:

- the system is based on a material product (economic resource);
- all systems are human-centered and therefore interconnected;
- each system consists of a number of specific elements, but their work is subject to common, global goals;
- the system has the ability to develop and adapt by creating new connections.

Taking into account the possibilities of cumulative interaction of the elements of the socio-economic system in the regional system and, conversely, the process of determining socio-economic needs, it is appropriate to pay attention to economic resources according to their structure and functional characteristics.

In our opinion, in view of the increasing complexity of the economic system, its economic resources are formed on the basis of the following classification:

- variable – resources in constant motion;
- developing - processes of interdependence and connection of resources contribute to the transition of quantitative changes to qualitative changes (direct development);
- flexible - in accordance with the external and internal conditions of the formation of territorial systems, it has preserved its characteristics in an optimal state with environmental changes;
- self-organizing - maintaining their stability (balance) in socio-economic processes.

Total economic resources are characterized by the existence of mutual causal relationships (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Structural elements of economic resources*

Source: developed by the author.

Only a detailed study of the influencing factors and the specific characteristics of their influence will serve the main strategic task of the region - comprehensive development of the regional socio-economic system.

A slightly different set of standard factors is currently adopted in the theory and practice of foreign countries. In this, two large groups of factors are distinguished: hard and soft factors.

Hard factors include quantitative factors:

- resource oriented (land, labor, capital);
- oriented to the production and sale of products (proximity of cooperation partners, infrastructure, population and consumption structure);
- established by the state (taxes, subsidies and support programs).

Figure 3. Factors affecting the state of formation of the territory*

Source: developed by the author.

Soft factors belong to categories that are difficult to measure quantitatively, including: the level of development of the social environment of the settlement, its "friendly" situation with the economy, the stability of the political situation and the social environment, the quality of the education system and such as the level of preparation are relevant. These factors are very important in modern conditions, and their influence on the socio-economic development of regions should be taken into account.

All influencing factors can be divided into controllable, uncontrollable and dependent factors. Factors that can be directly influenced by local authorities are controllable factors. Uncontrollable factors, on the other hand, include factors that are not dependent on the activities of local authorities or have very little influence on them. However, most of the factors combine characteristics of controllable and uncontrollable factors and can be classified as an intermediate group of related factors. The classification of factors according to the level of management is presented in Figure 3.

In our opinion, in the conditions of the innovative development of the economy, the formation of the management system of economic activity in industrial enterprises is carried out through the functional systems of the organization of the production process (Table 1).

Table 1

The main functional systems of the organization of production processes in industrial enterprises*

Systems of organization of the production process in the enterprise			
1. Organization of production activities	2. Organization of financial and economic indicators	3. Technical-technological organization	4. System of labor organization in the enterprise
Production process planning	Planning of technical and economic indicators	Organization of functional departments	System of planning and marketing research
Organization of forms of production	Management of fixed and working capital	Management of the organizational structure	The system of organizing the activities of workers
Regulation of production activities	Management of financial activities	Document flow control	The system of orientation and adaptation of workers to the profession
Organization of production	Accounting and reporting	Information flows and	System of training and

infrastructure		communications	development of workers
Organization of material and technical support	Conduct economic analysis	Necessary technical equipment and office furniture	System of organization of employee motivation
Transport and logistic service for production	International accounting standards. Management of business relations	Planning and organization of labor activities	Management of social development

Source: developed by the author.

Industry modeling of the resource management system and all its business processes in the enterprise allows to minimize the costs of achieving production efficiency and ensures intensive development. For this, the enterprise:

- ensuring the growth of labor productivity and labor intensity;
- increase the competence of the company's employees;
- development of industrial relations system;
- increase interest in labor results, implementation of the labor incentive program;
- to determine ways to improve the harmony and effectiveness of all elements of the organization of production processes in the enterprise;
- researching ways of rational, economical and effective use of economic resources;
- use of modern techniques and technologies for automation of document circulation in the human resource management system, etc

Determining and evaluating the impact of external factors on the effective use of economic resources in industrial production is important in the formation of their resource management system.

Factors of the external environment of industrial enterprises are manifested through systems that are related to each other and have an active influence on each other. These include the government, suppliers, customers, competitors, and market conditions as directly influencing factors. This group also includes the factors of rapid development of new forms and methods of communication, means of communication, technologies and equipment related to scientific and technical progress. In the process of decision-making in the field of human resources management, the above-mentioned external forces (factors)

have a direct impact on the structure of business in the field of industrial production.

M.Yu. Sheresheva stated that "at the current stage, network structures in the economy are facing many difficulties related to the specific characteristics of the institutional environment due to the previous development trajectory" [9].

State intervention in the economy is one of the most powerful influencing factors of the external environment. The instability of the legislative framework is compounded by the often inflexible nature of the republic's legal system.

External conditions do not directly affect the enterprise, but they can serve as an incentive or obstacle to the development of the resource management system, and this role depends on the organization's ability to analyze and evaluate the most important external environmental factors that affect enterprises[9].

At the same time, the organization of work also depends on internal factors, because they have an organizational nature and influence the implementation of policies. "The truth about resource management is that the strict constraints of the external environment force the enterprise to search for the "optimal point" where the overall effect is the most favorable, and to influence processes and technologies to achieve the opportunity through the "parallel" formation of internal factors - synergistic effect and forces the company to move to a new quality stage of the management system" [10].

The internal environment of the development of industrial enterprises - all resource possibilities - determines the potential and possibilities of organizing production processes. Enterprise resources are an element of the economic potential of industrial production enterprises [11]. Objectively, there is a constant lack of resources. Therefore, most manufacturing enterprises focus on intensive growth factors related to the introduction of innovations, rational use of resources. It is necessary to determine the possibilities of effective use of economic resources based on the development of a well-thought-out resource strategy.

In our opinion, the internal factors of management of economic resources and their effective use in industrial enterprises are as follows:

- development strategy of the enterprise. Choosing a management strategy that matches the company's strategy and developing directions for effective use of employees;

- the formation of the organizational culture of the enterprise: the formation of the organizational culture in the industrial enterprise is carried out

by introducing new approaches and methods, coordinating it with the level of development of production forces;

- determining the optimal amount of expenses in the use of financial and financing opportunities of the industrial enterprise and economic resources and reducing its relative level;

- approaches to the effective use of resources in an industrial enterprise: creates conditions for development to the level of branching for enterprises that do not have a network of technologies and skills used in the effective use of resources;

- description of the quantity and quality of economic resources and their future transformation directly affects the quality level of production;

- production capacity of the industrial enterprise and its territorial location.

Conclusions and suggestions

In our opinion, management methods and technologies for effective use of economic resources in industrial enterprises and resource management entities include:

- first, leaders who organize economic activity and directly control its results;

- secondly, leaders responsible for the use of economic resources;

- thirdly, top managers who carry out strategic management in the company;

- fourth, performance of a specific task by the component or unit responsible for the use of economic resources, implementation of activity directions and technologies, and evaluation of prospective efficiency.

Therefore, all internal factors are influenced by the external environment, act interdependently and require "reconstruction". Under the influence of external environmental factors, organizational culture, the quantity and quality of resources, the amount of funds allocated for the use and maintenance of resources, and other such internal environmental factors can be indirectly influenced.

In general, ensuring the efficiency of resource management is achieved by fully coordinating the available resources, methods and measures of working with them to the requirements of the external environment. Depending on the performance of the resource management system, a decision is made on the need to update (reorganize) or improve it.

In conclusion, for the development of industrial production, it is necessary to improve the effective use of economic resources and their management system, which is achieved by changing the management system accordingly and moving to a new quality stage. Therefore, the development of the system of efficient use of resources in enterprises is achieved by ensuring a qualitative change in their management technologies, methods and principles.

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